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ESIRA — ENHANCING SOCIAL INNOVATION IN RURAL AREAS

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REGIONAL REPORT ON SOCIAL EXCLUSION AND SOCIAL ECONOMY INITIATIVES IN RURAL AREAS

Kongsvinger region – Norway

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1. Introduction

The main aim of this report has been to collect information regarding the situation of rural areas and the communities residing in each of the participating regions in the ESIRA project (ENHANCING SOCIAL INNOVATION IN RURAL AREAS HORIZON 101136253). These reports will act as the basis of D4.1, “Benchmark study on social exclusion in rural areas,” and D4.2, “Multi-level analysis of social economy initiatives in rural areas”.

This report seeks to go beyond available literature and statistical data and, together with the organisations participating in the pilots, explore the situation in the regions and the drivers behind their disadvantages.

The report introduces the territorial organisation of Norway and analyses the situation of people living in rural areas, with a particular focus on territorial inequalities.

A deeper examination of the drivers of vulnerability and social exclusion in rural contexts was undertaken in the Kongsvinger Region. The analysis considers the social processes in the region and the livelihood opportunities at the municipal level. Existing assets and hidden resources in the municipality were assessed according to statistical data and the opinions of leading local stakeholders in the social economy.

2. Methodology

The methodological approach adopted in this report draws upon a mix of quantitative and qualitative indicators, including statistics, literature from different sources, and interviews. We conducted a search in Google Scholar, the Norwegian government database of documents, and Innlandet County website. We also asked colleagues in our network for advice on relevant literature (reports, regional plans, initiatives, strategies). Furthermore, we used the reference list in different documents to identify potentially relevant literature for further exploration.

To recruit participants for this report, we asked colleagues in our network and searched different websites for people who would have an informed perspective on the Kongsvinger Region or social exclusion. This included people with disabilities, local decision-makers, academics, those employed in local or regional administration, representatives of organizations or services, and different regional groups such as minorities or vulnerable groups. All participants were contacted through e-mail with information about the project and were able to consider whether they would like to participate. The interviews were conducted digitally via teams (5), in person (1), and over the telephone (2). They were conducted as individual interviews except for one focus group with two participants. The participants consented that the interviews were to be audio-recorded. Semi-structured interviews were conducted based on questions taken from the report template.

Most of the statistical data included in this report is from two sources. The first source is Statistics Norway, which is the National Statistical Institute of Norway, and the main producer of official statistics in the country. Statistics Norway has a statistics bank with tables, allowing you to customise your own table according to geographical level (national, regional or municipal) and time series, and selecting

drill-down options including gender, age and other demographical variables. Accordingly, in this report we reference Statistics Norway and the relevant tables we have exported. More information about Statistics Norway is available at their site.

The second source widely used in this report is Innlandsstatistikk (Innlandet Statistics). This is a site that creates statistical reports and analysis customised for Innlandet, its regions and municipalities and businesses. One of the reasons we have used Innlandsstatistikk as a source is that it offers ready-made statistical tables and graphs of the Kongsvinger Region. We don't find statistic tables and graphs on this level at Statistics Norway. In addition, Innlandsstatistikk combines statistics from different sources, such as statistics from the Norwegian state's Labour and Welfare Administration (NAV), The Norwegian Institute of Public Health (NIPH), The Norwegian Directorate for Education and Training, and several other data sources.

The ESIRA study in the Norwegian context was approved by the Norwegian Agency for Shared Service in Education and Research, reference number [828076], and the Research Ethics Committee of the University of Innlandet Norway, reference number [24/01109]. All the participants in the interviews signed a consent form. They were informed of their right to withdraw from the study without stating a reason and that confidentiality would be maintained in any publications resulting from this study. All the participants received the written consent form that included information about the project team and what would be required if they agreed to participate.

3. Country overview: Norway

3.1 Territorial system of the country

In Norway the total area of land and fresh water, including Svalbard and Jan Mayen, is **384,482 km²**. Mainland Norway is 323,806 km² (Statistics Norway, 2024f). The current population of the country is 5,562,363 as of May 22, 2024 (Statistics Norway, 2023d).

There are **15 counties and 357 municipalities** in Norway (Regjeringen, 2024). Innlandet county is Norway's largest county with an area of 52,072.4 km² and it has the greatest number of municipalities (Innlandsstatistikk, 2024c). The smallest county is Oslo with an area of 454,12 km². Municipalities in Norway vary in respect to their size, population and centrality. The most crowded municipality is Oslo, with a population of 709,037 (Statistics Norway, 2023d). The cities in Northern Norway are relatively scattered, and there is a sparse population in the surrounding municipalities. Statistics Norway's **centrality index** is an important tool ranking municipalities according to population's access to work and different types of services. The index has sub-indexes focusing on how many jobs those who live in each basic district can reach by car within a 90-minute radius, and how many service functions can be reached by those who live in each basic district by car within a similar radius (Høydahl, 2020). Oslo is ranked as the most central municipality. The municipalities surrounding Oslo have a high ranking. Utsira, which is an isolated island municipality, has the lowest value on the centrality index. Many of the other most remote municipalities are island municipalities or those that have settlements on islands without a mainland connection in the form of a bridge or tunnel such as Træna, Rødøy, Solund, Lurøy, Hasvik, Loppa, Røst and Leka (Kommunal- og moderniseringsdepartementet, 2021a).

Figure 1: Municipalities grouped according to their centrality

Source: Made by the authors, Data:(Statistics Norway, 2023c) and Geovekst.

There are **three levels of government** in Norway, comprising central government, county authorities, and municipalities. At the governmental level, it is the Ministry of Local Government and Regional Development, which is responsible for housing policy, the Planning and Building Act, local government finances and local administration, ICT Policy and Public Sector Reform, rural and regional policy, the conduct of elections, government employer policy, Sami and Minority Affairs and national mapping and geo-data policy (Kommunal- og distriktsdepartementet, 2024).

Local self-governance is an important principle in Norway. National regional and rural policy is primarily implemented with the support of self-governed municipal authorities (Angell et al., 2016).

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Since the 1950s, the efforts to transform municipalities into key components of the welfare state have increased the level of interaction between state and municipalities (Angell et al., 2016).

Currently, the relation between municipalities and the Norwegian state is regulated by an Act concerning municipalities and county authorities (The Local Government Act, 2018). The law states that ‘, each municipality and county authority is a separate legal entity and can make decisions on its own initiative and responsibility’ (The Local Government Act, 2018, §2-1). **Municipalities have considerable responsibility**, mostly concerning the offering of welfare services, such as childcare, primary education, health care and social services.

3.2 Strategies and policies

In 2021, the Norwegian government launched its **strategy for small towns and larger settlements/urban areas**¹. The government’s strategy places an emphasis upon the importance of strong small towns and larger settlements/urban areas as attractive places to live and work. The aim of this strategy is to help strengthen these areas as important centres for their regions, and to ensure regional balance (Kommunal- og moderniseringsdepartementet, 2021b).

The Norwegian Ministry of Local Government and Regional Development’s report to the Norwegian Parliament (Stortinget) is titled “A good life throughout Norway – regional and rural policy for the future.” It outlines both completed and upcoming policy initiatives concerning regional and rural Norway. Accordingly, the overall goal for rural and regional policy is that, “people should be able to live a good life throughout Norway, that all local communities should have room for development and creation of value, and that the population should increase in rural municipalities.” (Meld. St. 27, (2022-2023)). It is stated that the government works to make sure that people will have **access to work, housing and good services close to where they live**. Through **decentralized solutions**, the government aims to facilitate vibrant and sustainable local communities all around Norway (Meld. St. 27, (2022-2023), p. 6).

Another important development strategy is prepared by the **Youth District Panel** (Distrikssenteret, 2022), consisting of ten young people between the ages of 14-23.

In cooperation with the Centre of Competence on Rural Development, the Panel presents ten pieces of advice on future districts policy in Norway (Distrikssenteret, 2022). These pieces of advice emphasize that young people need access to work communities, work experience and varied workplaces in rural areas, and that schools should have a decentralized structure. Furthermore, the advice offered by the panel suggests safer roads, as well as widespread systems for on-demand transportation. Issues such as stable and secure high-speed mobile network, as well as measures that help young people settle in rural areas are among the recommendations.

¹ In Norway, a settlement/urban area refers to a collection of houses where at least 200 people live, and the distance between houses should not exceed 50 meters (Statistics Norway, 2023c).

Regional plan for an inclusive Innlandet (Innlandet fylkeskommune, 2023): Regional planning work is anchored in the Innlandet Strategy, which was adopted by the County Council in 2020. The strategy is based on the UN's 17 Sustainable Development Goals and constitutes the base for the work on the Regional Plan for an inclusive Innlandet region. The plan is designed for 4 years and looks towards 2030. The goal of the plan is to set the direction for social development and ensure that the Innlandet region offers an open and inclusive society for everyone, both economically, socially, culturally and ethnically. In this plan inclusion means participating on equal terms in social communities, having equal opportunities to succeed (everyone should have access to the necessary resources, support, and training to acquire the skills and knowledge needed to succeed) and being able to influence the rules and regulations of the local community. Furthermore, inclusion means that everybody can take part in education, participate in employment, as well as be actively included in the social and cultural everyday life of the community (Innlandet fylkeskommune, 2023).

We all need a safe place to call home – National strategy for social housing policies 2021-2024 (Ministry of Local Government and Modernisation, 2021): This strategy aims to help those who are disadvantaged in the housing market. The strategy outlines the following priorities: No one shall be homeless; children and young people shall have good living conditions; people with disabilities shall, like everybody else, have the opportunity to choose where and how they would like to live. The strategy is particularly important for the development of housing in rural areas. Regarding this issue, in 2019 the Norwegian State Housing Bank and the Centre of Competence on Rural Development launched a three-year cooperation project on the development of age-friendly housing in rural districts. The aim of this project is to identify barriers to the building of such housing in rural districts, review the development of new measures and help to realise specific housing projects. Another important issue covered in the strategy is the loan schemes to support housing construction in rural districts. It is argued that a limited range of housing may hinder recruitment of labour in rural districts, and therefore the goal is to promote a more flexible and varied range of housing opportunities in rural districts (Ministry of Local Government and Modernisation, 2021).

Grants for social entrepreneurship and social entrepreneurs: Grants were launched in 2011 by the State administered body, The Norwegian Labour and Welfare Administration (NAV). The goal of the scheme is to stimulate the development of social entrepreneurship geared towards combating poverty and social exclusion in Norway (Arbeids- og velferdsetaten, 2024). The Directorate of Labor and Welfare reviewed the grant scheme in 2011–2013, leading to revised regulations in 2014. In 2017, 24 entities received grants, with nearly half focusing on children and youth. Other target groups include individuals with substance abuse issues, former addicts, released prisoners, immigrants, and those with mental health challenges (Arbeids-og velferdsetaten, 2024).

Support from Innovation Norway: Innovation Norway supports social entrepreneurship by providing funding. They also offer advisory services and networking opportunities aiming to support entrepreneurs in the development of sustainable business models (Arbeids- og velferdsetaten, 2024).

Grants for the inclusion of children and young people: This funding is provided by The Norwegian Directorate for Children, Youth and Family Affairs (Bufdir). The goal of the scheme is to make it possible

for all children and young people to have the opportunity to participate in society. Public organizations, voluntary organizations and private actors can apply for the grant for activities to support children and young people who, for various reasons, are at risk of social exclusion (Barne-ungdoms- og familiedirektoratet, 2024).

3.3 Territorial inequalities in Norway

The **northernmost region of Norway** faces unique regional development challenges not found in other parts of the country. This region is unique due to its **significant geographical distances and low population**, and this poses distinct challenges (Norwegian Ministry of Local Government and Regional Development, 2013). In addition to that, **climate-related issues** play an important role in these regions. They experience harsh climate, characterized by a short growing season, and have a soil with limited agricultural potential (Gløersen et al., 2006). When it comes to climate changes, Arctic regions of Norway face particular challenges because permafrost, prevalent in most of the Arctic, is increasingly thawing. A survey conducted between 2019 and 2020 in the Arctic region also collected data from other Arctic regions including Longyearbyen, Svalbard (Norway), located in the Arctic Ocean. The findings revealed that most of the 237 participants are aware of the landscape changes due to the thawing of the permafrost and how this connected with rising air temperatures. While they generally view permafrost thaw negatively, they don't see it as a challenge in all aspects of life (Ramage et al., 2022).

The research report “Mountain areas and mountain municipalities in southern Norway: Definition, delimitation and characterization” (Arnesen et al., 2010), provides a useful resource mapping on themes concerning access to services, demography and working life in mountain areas and municipalities in Norway. The analysis of demographic conditions shows that the **mountain municipalities** have experienced a negative demographic development since 1990, largely in contrast to other municipalities in southern Norway and in contrast to the national average. The mountain areas and municipalities in southern Norway vary when it comes to the registered numbers of those employed and unemployed. Overall, there are a low number of registered unemployed, but also a low proportion of employed people (Arnesen et al., 2010). Regarding access to selected public services (airport, railway, hospital and university and schools), the study shows that municipalities in Southern Norway that have worst accessibility to the public services mentioned in the study.

Another territorial inequality is related to housing opportunities. The lack of access to suitable housing is a barrier to recruitment and growth for both private and municipal employers in rural municipalities (Gyene et al., 2020). A survey from 2020, covering 147 district municipalities, shows that businesses in every fourth rural municipality report challenges related to recruiting labour. And, this is partly due to the lack of suitable housing, and that housing shortages are identified as a significant cause of recruitment difficulties.

Recognizing the differences between district and urban environments is essential in addressing the challenges faced by youth in these areas. Traditional rural industries, such as agriculture, fishing, tourism, and natural resource extraction, generally have lower wage levels than urban industries. As a

result, rural youth grow up in households that, on average, have fewer economic capital resources compared to those of urban youth (Rye, 2019). Moreover, district communities are often characterized by dispersed populations and long distances to both public and private services. For example, many primary school students in these areas have long commutes, which may become even longer when they begin secondary education (Rye, 2019).

Regarding NEET (young people who are Not in Education, Employment or Training) it is reported that differences in NEET rates between municipalities with high and low centralization are small (Rydland & Labriola, 2022). However, there are disparities in NEET rates among population groups, with immigrants and those with low education levels being overrepresented. NEET rates also vary between Norwegian counties, with the highest rates in Oslo or Vestfold and Telemark (Rydland & Labriola, 2022).

3.4 Social economy

In Norway, the phrase “social economy” is normally used to refer to the social science of economics, rather than to a sub-sector of organisations. The Norwegian language lacks nuanced terms for social enterprise, making no clear distinction between a "social entrepreneur"—an individual who drives social innovation—and a "social enterprise"—a structured organisation with social or idealistic goals. Accordingly, the term "sosial entreprenør" is used to describe both in Norway, although it's important to recognize and treat them as distinct concepts (Hulgård 2017, cited in Kobro, 2019). In our society, it is possible to argue that social entrepreneurship and social enterprises in Norway are still in its early stages of development. There is no legal framework governing the activity of such organizations, nor any specific organizational structure designated for social enterprises (see also Enjolras, Andersen, et al., 2021, p. 309). The policy development in this field has been scarce (Engedahl & Loga, 2024).

Even though Norway has a long history of different types of **cooperatives**, it is worth noting that cooperatives are a form of organization that is not widespread in Norway compared to other countries (Loga, 2016). For example, Norway has some use of consumer-cooperatives within food retail. Historically cooperatives were important actors in the housing sector in the post-war period. Within agriculture production cooperatives have also been important, many of today's large food producers organised as cooperatives owned by producers, particularly within meat and dairy production.

In the 2000s, social entrepreneurship and social enterprises began to emerge as concepts with inspiration from countries that had a strong history of social economy and cooperatives. These countries had experience with organizations that combined “volunteering and business” and also inspiration from countries with a stronger tradition of private, both non-profit and commercial, welfare production (Loga, 2016, p. 22).

In January 2008 the Cooperative Societies' Act (Samvirkelova, 2008) came into force and it is a Norwegian law regulating cooperatives. Prior to this, “the regulation of cooperatives was based on non-statutory law and other relevant laws. The Cooperative Act brings together the several related practices concerning cooperatives into a single law” (Store norske leksikon, 2024). Cooperatives have in recent years had to adapt to changing market conditions. Developments within the housing sector

have been most noticeable. As the Norwegian housing market became increasingly liberalised from the mid-1980s, housing cooperatives also followed suit and become market and profit oriented and were less oriented towards social goals (Sørvoll & Bengtsson, 2016).

Table 1: Number of cooperatives and number of employees – a 10-year perspective

Source: (Statistics Norway, 2024e)

	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Number of registered cooperatives	544	798	810	815	813	791	773	651	601	585	554
Number of people employed by cooperatives	33,825	34,360	34,902	36,363	36,346	37,354	37,230	36,884	35,735	35,663	34,981

The most opportunities for employment in social enterprises are found in the industry and retail sectors. Of those employed in cooperatives, 65% worked within retail and 29% in industry.

Table 2: Overview of different companies, divided into Norway, Innlandet and Kongsvinger region

	Norway		Innlandet		Kongsvinger region	
	All registered companies	All companies with registered employees	All registered companies	All companies with registered employees	All registered companies	All companies with registered employees
Foundations ("Stiftelser")	5,924	1,556	169	31	26	6
Cooperatives ("Samvirkeforetak")	6,377	1,384	113	41	15	2
Associations ("Forening/lag/innretning")	112,015	5,312	2,162	134	328	14

Source: (The Brønnøysund Register Center, 2024)

In Norway, social initiatives are based on extensive civic and social engagement, primarily conducted within the framework of member-based voluntary organizations (Meld. St. 32, (2020-2021)). Since 2008, Norway has seen an increased interest in **social entrepreneurship** and social enterprise among both actors and organizations (Eimhjellen & Loga, 2016). The **voluntary sector** is typically composed of small entities with few employees and limited turnovers, whereas **non-profit organizations** are

normally larger and more professionally organised, and adapt to the market and social innovations through project development (Eimhjellen & Loga, 2016). The growth and history of social entrepreneurship in Norway has two distinct drivers: innovative joint-stock companies on the one hand, and the voluntary sector and large non-profit organizations involved in social work or related professions, on the other hand (Meld. St. 32, (2020-2021)). The field is dominated by these two organizational forms, driven by various targeted grant schemes directed to these two organizational forms in particular. Innovation Norway, that is previously mention in the report, is “the Norwegian Government's most important instrument for innovation and development of Norwegian enterprises and industry” (Innovation Norway, 2024). Innovation Norway distributes grants to joint-stock companies and thereby stimulates the growth of joint-stock companies. Many organizations in Norway choose to become private limited companies (joint-stock companies) in order to be able to apply for grants through Innovation Norway (Eimhjellen & Loga, 2016).

The Government acknowledges that voluntary organizations and social entrepreneurs are important partners that contribute to social inclusion and participation in society by, for example, offering different pathways into working life (Meld. St. 32, (2020–2021)). The Norwegian welfare state is extensive and covers most social and welfare needs in society. The social care service is mainly provided by public actors and functions as a public system for work inclusion, covering tasks that in many other countries are left to private and voluntary/non-profit actors (Eimhjellen & Loga, 2016). There are several work inclusion social enterprises in Norway that offer work opportunities to people with disabilities. It is difficult to argue that social enterprises have emerged in niche areas, because most social enterprises focus on a wide range of issues such as, work integration, support for children, adolescents, refugees, and elderly care. They offer diverse services, utilise a spectrum of models and relationships with the public sector—some sell services to government bodies, while others rely on grants from local authorities (Enjolras, Loga, et al., 2021).

In the past few years, several political initiatives have been launched to promote the growth of this field in Norway, but there has been relatively little policy development. There has been increased awareness of the need to enhance employment inclusion and to develop new businesses, fostering innovation, and promoting entrepreneurship. It also involves restructuring the welfare state to support diversity in service provision, improve service quality, and encourage active citizenship. In some areas, there are social needs that the welfare state cannot fully address, and it is often in these areas that social entrepreneurs can collaborate with public services (Eimhjellen & Loga, 2016).

In 2008 The Centre for Research on Civil Society and Voluntary Sector was established and is a collaboration between the Institute for Social Research and NORCE Norwegian Research Centre. The Centre is state-funded², and its objective has been to conduct independent and socially relevant research on voluntary engagement and voluntary organizations in Norway and to thereby develop and

² Funded by the Ministry of Culture, the Ministry of Justice and Public Security, the Ministry of Health and Care Services, the Ministry of Children and Equality, and the Ministry of Labour and Social Affairs.

disseminate research-driven knowledge to decision-makers, other researchers, and the general public (Samfunnsforskning, 2021).

If we look at organizations registered in the public registry of voluntary organisations in Norway, there were about 70 000 registered organisations in June 2024 (Digitaliseringsdirektoratet, 2024). If we look at how many of these that there were registered with one or more full-time employees, it accounts for about 8 % (5816 out of 70019).

Larger Publicly regulated support schemes have contributed to much of the growth in the voluntary sector (Arnesen & Sivesind, 2017). One of the larger important public funding sources for voluntary organizations is the program called Grasrotandelen (**The Grassroot Share**). This is a program that allows players of the Norwegian National Lottery to allocate a portion of their betting stakes to a local organization, registered in the Voluntary Register. This program was established in 2009, and the purpose of Grasrotandelen is to promote voluntary activities at local or regional levels in Norway. Entities must be non-profit and primarily based on voluntary efforts to participate in the Grasrotandelen (Forskrift om grasrotandel, 2023; Norsk Tipping, 2024). Out of the 70 000 organizations currently registered on the Voluntary Register, 59 % are considered eligible for participation in the Grasrotandelen program. It is interesting to note that of the 70 000 organizations in the Voluntary Register, the most common type of organizations are “Recreation and social associations” (20 %), sports organizations (19 %), and art and culture organizations (17 %). About 2 % have inclusion and diversity registered as their “main category”.

In Innlandet, there are 8186 organizations registered on the Voluntary Register, and in the Kongsvinger Region there are 743. Of these 743 registered organizations, 70 % are eligible for participating in the Grasrotandelen program. In the Kongsvinger region **sport organizations** constitute the highest share of the categories (21 %), followed by recreation and social associations (19 %), and art and culture organizations (16%). About 1 % (9 organizations) have inclusion and diversity registered as their “main category”. Even though 1 % is a low proportion, there might be other organizations that also work indirectly with social inclusion, without having “inclusion” registered as the main category. Among the 78 organizations (10 %) in the Kongsvinger Region registered in the category “community development” one might expect an interest in preventing exclusion.

If we don’t look only at the Voluntary Register, but also look at other sources, there is a satellite account for non-profit institutions in Norway from 2018 that, though slightly dated, may still be of some relevance. The satellite account is based on national accounts and a sample survey and, therefore, does not estimate the number of institutions. The 2018 figures in the table below show an output of 117 844 million NOK (12 279 million EUR), and a value add of 61 526 million NOK (6 411 million EUR). The number of hours put into these institutions is estimated to have a value equivalent of 89 161 full-time paid employees.

In Table 3, we see that in 2018 almost 45 % of the funding of non-profit institutions came from households, and almost 27 % came from central government. 16,7 % of the funding came from local or municipal governments.

These figures will be updated with 2022 figures in the beginning of 2025.

Table 3: Satellite account for non-profit institutions 2018, Norway.

	2018
Output in millions	NOK: 117,844 EUR: 12,279
Value added in millions	NOK: 61,526 EUR: 6,411
Full-time equivalent persons (paid employees)	89,161
Percentage of GDP	
Value added as share of GDP (%)	1.7
Value added as share of GDP Mainland Norway (%)	2
Full-time equivalent persons (paid employees) as share of total full-time equivalent persons in Norway (%)	3.6
Sources of income for non-profit institutions	
Central government's share of total funding (%)	26.6
Local/municipal governments' share of total funding (%)	16.7
Households' share of total funding (%)	44.9
Other sources of funding. Share of total funding (%)	11.9

Source: (Statistics Norway, 2020)

3.5 Social enterprises in Norway

The Nordic welfare system is characterized by a division of labour between the voluntary sector and the state. Put simply, welfare state policies are “the historical and institutional backdrop for the emergence of social enterprise in Norway” (Enjolras, Loga, et al., 2021, p. 166). Norway, like the other Nordic countries, has a social-democratic welfare state with a large public sector that emphasizes equal income distribution and gender equality (Enjolras, Loga, et al., 2021). Historically, from 1850 and onwards, the voluntary organisations played a significant role in providing “[...] public-health education, created and ran hospitals and clinics, offered treatment and care for the sick and disabled, and offered a channel for citizens to participate in policy-making” (Enjolras, Loga, et al., 2021, p. 167). The development of the welfare state was, amongst other things, directed towards the state take-over of “[...] responsibility for a large amount of institutions and projects in the welfare sector that voluntary

service organizations had previously managed in their own or in which they had played an important part” (Selle et al., 2018, p.121).

The rise of social enterprises in Norway has its origins in both the voluntary and business sectors (Kobro, 2019). Currently, it is in an emerging phase in Norway and has become a topic on the national policy agenda (Enjolras, Loga, et al., 2021). There is a **broad and lively debate** about the involvement of commercial actors in the Norwegian welfare system, as political and financial support is provided to private welfare service delivery, including social enterprises (NOU 2024:1). Voluntarism and non-profit objectives have the backing of all political parties and the general public. However, a level of confusion is evident as social enterprises pursue both social/non-profit and commercial objectives. The general **uncertainty** surrounding social entrepreneurship and social enterprise is crucial for understanding this emerging policy field in Norway (Kobro, 2019). This is further described by Kobro (2019).

The new praxis of some voluntary organisations, which include social entrepreneurship in their service portfolio, represents so far, an exception. It does not constitute a dominant pattern. Only a handful of the old philanthropic organisations have initiated activities that can be considered as part of the spectrum of social enterprise practices. Instead, individuals and small groups in local communities initiate many new experiments implementing social innovations. **However, in Norway as in the other Nordic countries, social innovations are most often accomplished in close cooperation with the public sector, particularly the local authorities** (Kobro 2019, 15).

A large number of social enterprises in Norway are organised as voluntary associations, but the most common legal form among them is “Ideelt Aksjeselskap, a non-profit limited company” (Kobro, 2019, p. 18). According to Enjolras et.al., (2021) “there is no recognition, in terms of legal status, of social enterprise as a specific type of economic and social entity” (Enjolras, Loga, et al., 2021, p. 171).

The non-profit limited company is a specific Norwegian legal form used for limited companies whose statutes include a set of rules regulating the return on investments outside a strict profit organisational regime. [...] the non-profit limited company is not a separate organisational form (Kobro, 2019, p .18).

There is **no official specific register** of social enterprises in Norway. However, there have been conducted mappings of social enterprises that have provided an overview (Eimhjellen – Loga, 2016; Kobro et al., 2017; Kobro, 2019).

Kobro (2019) has stated that *“the final list of 295 Norwegian social enterprises proves as reliable as possible in the Norwegian context”* (p. 28). Not all social enterprises consider themselves as a social enterprise, which contributes to a source of possible bias. The majority of the 295 social enterprises are operated as limited companies and voluntary organizations (Kobro, 2019). Norwegian social enterprises generate income through various activities, including education, food services, forestry, waste recycling, building maintenance, manufacturing, and more. These enterprises often serve local and regional public entities, particularly in providing welfare services (Kobro, 2019).

Enjolras et al. (2021) have developed a model that displays how social enterprises may be distinguished in Norway, see Tabel 4. Model 1, entrepreneurial non-profit, and Model 2, social venture, differentiate by legal form, main resources, governance, and structure (Enjolras, Loga, et al., 2021) .

Table 4: Characteristics of the two main SE models in Norway

Ideal type	Model 1: Entrepreneurial non-profit	Model 2: Social venture
Main legal form	Voluntary association or foundation	Limited-liability company
Main resources	Public grants and contracts	Market income, public and private grants
Governance	Democratic	Entrepreneurial
Main support structure	Umbrella welfare	Venture philanthropists

Source: Enjolras et al., 2021, p. 171.

There are many companies in the Kongsvinger Region that might fit the social enterprise category. We choose to highlight two examples, Eskoleia and Vekstbedriften Vilja, which we consider relevant examples as the Kongsvinger Region is known for being an industrial area. These entities take this as a point of departure and thereby contribute to inclusion through employment.

Eskoleia AS is a company based in Kongsvinger. They specialize in producing various steel products. This company is called “Arbeidsinkluderingsbedrift,” which translates as “Employment inclusion enterprise.” In addition to producing steel products, they focus on integrating individuals into the workforce, particularly those who may face barriers to employment (Eskoleia, 2004). Eskoleia emphasizes that employment inclusion is their social responsibility. They contribute towards individuals securing employment for the first time or a new job opportunity for those who have work experience. There are different reasons why someone faces challenges with obtaining employment; it might be health-related or difficulties adjusting to new jobs. Eskoleia helps in the transition and provides the necessary support as an employment inclusion enterprise.

Vekstbedriften Vilja AS is a growth company in Eidskog. This company offers a variety of services and produces several products, such as copy center, canteen/ providing food services, producing firewood, aluminum work, stainings services for wood products and so on. Vekstbedriften Vilja AS targets those who are between 18-30 years old, who must demonstrate activity obligations in order to receive social benefits from the National Labour and Welfare Administration and who are additionally outside of the workforce. The initiative involves organized work training and guidance. Each participant has an Individual plan. Supported work guidance is offered, along with work training in Vilja or in an ordinary company able to make adjustment to ensure personalised support. The goal is to strengthen the opportunities to obtain work or enter education. Their core business is to develop individuals and give them the chance to lead an active, professional life, but they also produce services and goods worth about 10 million NOK annually (Vekstbedriften Vilja, 2024).

4. Regional overview – Kongsvinger Region

4.1 Geographic and historical aspects

Innlandet is the **largest county** in Norway in area, covering nearly one-fifth of Norway’s mainland area. Within the 52,000 km² you find 46 municipalities with about 376,000 inhabitants. Innlandet county is part of Eastern Norway and is the only county in Norway without a coastline. The county is sparsely populated, with many municipalities having low centrality, often facing challenges typically associated with remote communities. A notable trend is an increasing elderly population and a decline in younger people, with a continued movement towards Mjøsbyene (cities around the long Mjøsa Lake) and local regional centres. As the country's **largest agricultural county**, Innlandet contributes 20% of Norway's total agricultural production and 40% of the timber harvested from Norwegian forests. It is a key region for the green bioindustry and has a diverse economy with strong technology and industry sectors, leading brands in tourism, and nationally leading for training in information security. The county boasts the country's highest mountain, longest river, largest lake, and 11 national parks, either fully or partially located within its borders.

Innlandet has a large number of part-time residents due to its status as the country's largest holiday cottage county, with about 90,000 units (Innlandsstatistikk, 2024d).

In ESIRA, we focus on the Kongsvinger Region within Innlandet County. The Kongsvinger Region is located in the **southern part of Innlandet County** and is situated close to the Swedish border. It comprises **six municipalities**: Kongsvinger, Eidskog, Sør-Odal, Nord-Odal, Grue, and Åsnes. Kongsvinger serves as the central hub for the region.

4.2 Demography

As of the first quarter of 2024, the population of the Kongsvinger Region was 49,073.

Figure 2: Population in the six municipalities of Kongsvinger Region, by 1st quarter of 2024

Source: (Innlandsstatistikk, 2024d)

Generally, there has been a **slight overall decrease in population** in the Kongsvinger Region in recent decades. In the past two years there has been a slight increase in the population, largely due to **immigrants** from Ukraine.

Figure 3: Development of population in the Kongsvinger Region, from 1998 to 2024.

Source: (Innlandsstatistikk, 2024d)

“**The green heart of Norway**” is the nickname for this region, due to the large forest areas, wooded hills and cultivated land. Norway’s longest river, Glomma, runs through the region, and has played an important part in the settlement and industrial history of the area. The vast contiguous forest area of Finnskogen (the Finn Forest) is also a part of this region. Historically, the Finnskogen-area is associated with **Finnish immigrants**, known as «Skogfinner» (Forest Fins), who settled there in the 1600s. Skogfinner came mainly from Savolax in Finland. Today, Skogfinner are recognized as one of the five national minorities in Norway.

The Kongsvinger Region, with its six municipalities, has the following villages/local communities: Magnor (Eidskog), Skotterud (Eidskog), Kongsvinger (Kongsvinger), Roverud (Kongsvinger), Skarnes (Sør-Odal), Sander (Sør-Odal), Disenå (Sør-Odal), Kirkenær (Grue), Mo (Nord-Odal), Flisa (Åsnes), and Kjellmyra (Åsnes). Only Kongsvinger holds the status of a «city» in this region.

The Kongsvinger Region is notable for its sparse population, both in terms of population density in persons by km² but also measured in percentage of households in sparsely populated areas (defined as clusters with less than 200 residences).

Table 5: Population Density

Municipality	Population density (population by km2)	Share of population in sparsely populated areas
Kongsvinger	19	26
Nord-Odal	10	69
Sør-Odal	17	60
Eidskog	10	61
Grue	6	73
Åsnes	7	70

Source: Statistics Norway (2024d, 2024k, 2024l)

The population composition in the Innlandet County, and the Kongsvinger Region, is a challenge. Both the county, and the Kongsvinger Region, struggle with a **skewed composition**. The population share in the working age (in Norway this is considered to be the age 20-66), as well as the child population share, is decreasing. The old age population share (in Norway often considered from 67+, as this is the ordinary retirement age) is increasing both in Innlandet County and in the Kongsvinger Region.

Figure 4: Development in number of people over the age of 67 in the Kongsvinger Region.

Source: (Innlandsstatistikk, 2024d)

Innlandet is the county in Norway with the **highest share of old population**. The Innlandet County and the Kongsvinger Region has a higher share of old population, than of child population. This is a trend that is expected to be a reality for Norway as a whole by 2030, while our pilot area is already experiencing this. Innlandet County is also the **only county in Norway with a “birth deficit”**, as there are fewer births each year than necessary to maintain the population size over time.

Figure 5: Development of the birth balance in the Kongsvinger Region from 1975 -2023.

Source: (Innlandsstatistikk, 2024d)

Population projections from Statistics Norway (2024) up to 2050 for the six municipalities in this region indicate that Nord-Odal and Åsnes will experience a decline in population, while Grue will experience zero growth. Eidskog and Kongsvinger is expected to show a small increase in population, but lower than the average for Innlandet County, and for Norway as a whole. Sør-Odal is the only municipality with a higher projected growth in population than the average for Innlandet County and Norway (Innlandsstatistikk, 2024d).

4.3 Economic situation

More people have Kongsvinger as a workplace rather than as a residence, while it is the opposite for the other five municipalities in this region. In 2023, Kongsvinger was the most common municipality for migration from the other municipalities in the region. The second most common municipality for migration for these municipalities (Sør-Odal, Eidskog, Nord-Odal, Åsnes and Grue) was Oslo, the capital of Norway. The domestic migration trend in all of Innlandet, including the Kongsvinger Region, is centralization. People move to either the largest municipality in the region, or the capital or largest cities in Norway.

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Figure 6: Difference in the number of employees. Workplace - residence. The difference is calculated as (number of employees with workplace) - (number of employees with residence) for each municipality

Source: (Innlandsstatistikk, 2024d)

The **migration balance** for Norway in 2023 was 52 578, and for Innlandet the migration balance for the same year was 3822 (Statistics Norway, 2024b).

Norway has a GDP per capita of 925,045 NOK in 2023. This converts to about 81,883 EUR, and is 73% higher than the EU average (Statistics Norway, 2023a). The GDP per capita decreased by 120 961 NOK (10,588 EUR) from 2022 to 2023 in Norway.

Table 6: GDP per region in Norway per 2021, in Euro

GEO (Labels)	Annual, Euro per inhabitant, 2021
Norway	78,700
Innlandet	48,100
Trøndelag	55,300
Nordland	53,800
Troms og Finnmark	54,500
Oslo	101,700
Viken	49,000

Vestfold og Telemark	48,400
Agder	49,700
Rogaland	65,300
Vestland	57,100
Møre og Romsdal	53,700

Source: (Eurostat, 2024)

Average yearly earnings in Norway were 668,700 NOK (58,531 EUR) in 2023. Average monthly earnings in 2023 were 56,360 NOK (4,933 EUR) There is a gender gap in the average earnings in Norway: in 2023 men had an average monthly earning of 59,460 NOK (5,204 EUR) while women had a monthly average earning of 52,530 NOK (4,598 EUR). This means that men on average had a higher monthly earning of 6,930 NOK (607 EUR) compared to women. Immigrants are reported to have lower monthly average earning than non-immigrants in Norway, with an average of 50,270 NOK (4,400 EUR) in 2023. Immigrants are, by Statistics Norway (Statistics Norway, 2024d), defined as persons who were born abroad, have foreign-born parents and grandparents and who have immigrated to Norway.

Looking at median household earnings, the municipalities in the Kongsvinger Region has lower earnings compared to Norway and the Innlandet Region.

Table 7: Total household income, Median (NOK and EUR) in 2022.

	Total household income, median 2022 in NOK	Total household income median 2022 in EUR
Norway	756,000	74,832
Innlandet	689,000	68,200
Kongsvinger	650,000	64,340
Nord-Odal	658,000	65,132
Sør-Odal	742,000	73,446
Eidskog	614,000	60,774
Grue	612,000	60,578
Åsnes	620,000	61,370

Source:(Statistics Norway, 2023b), ECB Eurosystem data portal

The Kongsvinger Region is one of Norway’s largest areas for forestry and agricultural activities. The long-term strategy for the region is to become a national leader in green growth and sustainability.

Table 8: Economic composition, share of employees in economic sector by activity (NACE).

Economic sector share of total employees within territorial units (2023 by 4. quarter)								
	Norway	Inlandet	Kongsvinger	Nord-Odal	Sør-Odal	Eidskog	Grue	Åsnes
Agriculture, forestry and fishing (NACE 01-03)	2	5	2	5	4	5	10	13
Secondary industry (NACE 05-43)	20	20	14	28	27	30	25	15
Service industry (NACE 45-82)	38	30	33	22	27	22	28	26
Public administration and defence; compulsory social security (NACE 84)	6	7	10	5	3	5	3	4
Education (NACE 85)	8	8	8	8	8	7	4	9
Human health and social work activities (NACE 86-88)	21	25	28	28	25	27	26	28
Personal services (NACE 90-99)	4	4	4	2	5	2	3	4
Unspecified (NACE 00)	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1

Source: Statistics Norway (2024j)

The region hosts industrial companies, including Mapei, Schütz, Glamox, and Bergene Holm. In this region there is an industrial cluster called 7 Sterke (the 7 Strong) that consists of over 90 companies that collectively have a turnover of 9,5 billion NOK (816,923,209 EUR) and account for over 4,000 jobs in the region (Kongsvingerregionen, 2024).

There are many reasons why this region is, and could become even more, relevant for businesses. The region has a strategically good location, being close to the capital (Oslo) and to Oslo Airport. The region is also close to Sweden and the EU. There is a growing innovation environment in the region, with Klosser Innovation and Sør-Hedmark Industrial Park providing incubation programs and targeted business development support. These programs offer access to professional business developers, capital, and networks, and seeks to support businesses grow. The six municipalities also cooperate to try to make the area attractive for businesses (Kongsvingerregionen, 2024).

Norwegian Confederation of Business (NHO) annually conducts a ranking exercise of the economic performance and business conditions in Norwegian municipalities and counties. NHOs ranking covers five key areas: 1) Business Environment: evaluates profitability and diversity in local businesses. 2) Labor Market: assesses employment rates and the availability of private sector jobs. 3) Demographics: looks at population trends and workforce age. 4) Competence: measures the education and skills of the workforce. 5) Municipal Economy: analyzes the financial health and sustainability of municipalities. The ranking is based on quantitative data from official statistics and aims to measure the attractiveness and growth potential for businesses in each area. The ranking is from 1 to 365, as there are 365 municipalities in Norway. In the ranking value 1 indicates best scores or highest attractiveness and growth potential for businesses, while 365 indicates the lowest attractiveness. The six municipalities

in the Kongsvinger Region are ranked from Kongsvinger at 201, to Eidskog ranked at 331. According to NHOs ranking the overall attractiveness of the region for businesses is in the lower end. One of the reasons why this region ends up with a fairly low ranked attractiveness for new businesses, despite having many businesses and support systems for businesses, appears to be the labour market in the region. Ranking of the labour market is based on indicators such as employment rate and share of disability pensioners, and the size of available work force (Næringslivets Hovedorganisasjon, 2023).

Table 9: Business attractiveness from NHO Norwegian Municipality Championship 2023.

	Ranking from 1 (highest attractiveness) to 365 (lowest attractiveness)
Kongsvinger	201
Nord-Odal	329
Sør-Odal	251
Eidskog	331
Grue	299
Åsnes	314

Source: (NHO, 2024)

Figure 7: Map of rankings of municipalities on the NHO Kommune-NM.

Source: Made by the authors, Data: (NHO, 2024), Geovekst.

In Norway, 2,845,307 people are employed, which constitutes 68,8 % of the population age 15-74 years old.

The **employment rates are slightly lower in Innlandet** (66,1 %) compared to the Norwegian average. This can be explained by a couple of reasons. First, around one-third of the fully unemployed in Innlandet have only completed basic education (grunnskolenivå), and many lack the skills that employers are looking for (Norwegian Labour and Welfare Administration, 2023). Second, most occupational groups have more fully unemployed job seekers than available positions. Consequently, there will always be a portion of the population that remains fully unemployed (Innlandsstatistikk,

2024b). The six municipalities in the Kongsvinger Region have a lower employment rate than both the Norwegian average and the average for Innlandet (Statistics Norway, 2024i).

The employment rate is **higher among men** than women in Innlandet, and in the Kongsvinger Region, as well as nationally. The largest gender gap is found in the municipality Nord-Odal in the Kongsvinger Region, where men have an employment rate of 65.3 while employment rates among women are 56.7.

Table 10: Employment rates 2023, in Norway, Innlandet and the municipalities in the Kongsvinger Region. Total and by gender

	Total	Men	Women
Norway	68.6	71.7	66
Innlandet	66.1	69.5	62.6
Kongsvinger	60.6	63.9	57.2
Nord-Odal	61.1	65.3	56.7
Sør-Odal	64.2	68.1	60.2
Eidskog	58.6	61.2	56.0
Grue	58.7	62.1	55.1
Åsnes	59.8	63.3	56.3

Source: (Statistics Norway, 2024i)

Figure 8: Index, development of employment from 2015, in Norway (purple), Innlandet (pink), and the Kongsvinger Region (turquoise). 2015=100

Source:(Innlandsstatistikk, 2024a)

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4.4 Institutional setting

266,196 of children in the age 1 to 5 are enrolled in kindergarten. This is 93,8 % of all children in this age range in Norway. If we only look at children in the age 3-5 age group, 97.5 % are enrolled in kindergartens. For Innlandet the shares are similar to the national levels, with 93,5 % of all children aged 1-5 years old enrolled in kindergarten.

Table 11: Share of children in the age 1-5 years old who are enrolled in kindergarten, in Norway, in Innlandet, and in the municipalities of the Kongsvinger Region (2023).

	Share of children 1-5 y.o. in kindergarten
Norway	93.8
Innlandet	93.5
Kongsvinger	95.1
Nord-Odal	90.2
Sør-Odal	96.2
Eidskog	86.2
Grue	86.4
Åsnes	87.5

Source:(Statistics Norway, 2024a)

49% of all kindergartens in Norway are public. In Innlandet **339 kindergartens** were registered in 2023, and out of these 192 were public, and 147 were private. This means that 57 % of the kindergartens in Innlandet are public.

The share of people over the age of 16 who have completed a university education in Norway was 37.4% in 2023. Innlandet is the county in Norway with the **lowest share of people with higher education**. The share of people who have completed a university education is lower in the Kongsvinger Region, than for the average in Innlandet and Norway.

Table 12: Share of people over the age of 16 who have completed a university or college education, 2023.

	Share of people over the age 16 with higher education
Norway	37.4
Innlandet	29.3
Kongsvinger	26.5
Nord-Odal	19.4
Sør-Odal	22.7
Eidskog	18.6
Grue	20.4
Åsnes	22

Source:(Innlandsstatistikk, 2024f; Statistics Norway, 2024c).

According to the report State of Health in the EU – Norway ([European Commission, 2021](#)), Norway has **good access to health care**. From this report we find that less than 1% of adults reported forgoing necessary medical care in 2019, which is about half the EU average. The same research report claims that Norway has an effective public health and primary care system, with good access to effective, high-quality treatments.

Table 13: Key figures, health care, Norway, Innlandet and the municipalities of the Kongsvinger Region, for 2023.

	Norway	Innlandet	Kongsvinger	Nord-Odal	Sør-Odal	Eidskog	Grue	Åsnes
Expenditure on municipal health and care services per inhabitant	NOK 36,844 EUR 3,225	NOK 44,002 EUR 3,851	NOK 41,159 EUR 3,603	NOK 48,456 EUR 4,648	NOK 40,653 EUR 3,900	NOK 53,708 EUR 5,152	NOK 57,965 EUR 5,560	NOK 53,333 EUR 5,116
Man-years in health and care per 10,000 inhabitants (man-years)	316.9	400.9	374.5	432.8	399.4	496.2	479.1	501.4
Net operating expenses for care services as a percentage of the municipality's total net operating expenses (percent)	34.2	40.1	40.2	49.6	36.1	43.9	53.6	44.7
Proportion of user-directed man-years in the care service w/ health education (percentage)	77.1	77.3	71.5	67.9	78.7	74.7	70.4	79.7
Man-years per user of care services (man-years)	0.60	0.55	0.52	0.54	0.45	0.43	0.42	0.45
Proportion of residents aged 80 and over who use home services (percentage)	26.9	28.7	26.4	27.6	29.3	38.7	32.9	31.5
Proportion of users of home services aged 0-66 (percent)	48.8	48.5	49.9	47.7	64.1	53.1	54.1	55.0
Proportion of residents aged 80 and over with institutional care (percentage)	10.1	9.8	9.4	12.4	9.8	6.7	7.9	13.1

Proportion of user-adapted private rooms with private bathroom/wc (percentage)	94.0	90.8	96.0	100.0	86.7	100.0	100.0	95.4
Expenses per day of stay in the institution NOK and EUR	NOK 5,155 EUR 451	NOK 5,209 EUR 456	NOK 4,418 EUR 387	NOK 4,386 EUR 384	NOK 5,216 EUR 457	NOK 5,002 EUR 438	NOK 5,002 EUR 438	NOK 4,115 EUR 360
Share of private institution places (percentage)	7.8	1.0	3.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Medical hours per week per nursing home resident (hours)	0.67	0.57	0.45	0.37	0.53	0.43	0.78	0.41
Proportion of residents aged 67-79 with daytime activity offers (percentage)	0.73	0.69	0.74	0.00	0.89	0.84	0.00	0.69
Net operating expenses for the municipal health service as a percentage of the municipality's total net operating expenses (percent)	6.1	6.5	5.2	5.4	5.8	6.0	5.6	8.6
Agreed physician man-years per 10,000 inhabitants (man-years)	12.6	13.7	13.8	14.4	10.5	11.6	11.7	16.1
Agreed physiotherapist man-years per 10,000 inhabitants (man-years)	9.6	11.3	11.5	10.0	12.9	12.7	10.6	13.8
Agreed man-years in the health center and school health service per 10,000 inhabitants 0-20 years (man-years)	53.4	58.3	50.4	78.5	72.5	45.6	24.3	97.0

Proportion of newborns with a home visit by a health nurse (percentage)	88.3	93.0	95.0	62.9	88.1	73.5	37.0	108.9
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Source: (Statistics Norway, 2024h)

Norway's mobility and transport system is designed to be efficient, sustainable, and accessible. The National Transport Plan 2022–2033 outlines the country's strategy to develop an efficient, environmentally friendly, and safe transport system by 2050 (Meld. St. 20, (2020-2021)). This plan emphasizes the integration of various modes of transport, including road, rail, and maritime, to reach the goal of seamless connectivity across the country. Norway also focuses on reducing greenhouse gas emissions through replacing fossil vehicles with electric vehicles and the development of the public transport infrastructure.

In Innlandet, the transport system aims to support both urban and rural connectivity. The region benefits from **well-maintained road networks and rail services** that link major towns and cities. The municipalities of Eidskog, Kongsvinger, Nord-Odal, Sør-Odal, Grue, and Åsnes are part of the Kongsvinger Region, which has been the focus of significant investments in infrastructure to enhance accessibility.

Compared to other Nordic countries and EU nations, Norway leads in the adoption of **electric vehicles** per capita (Nordic Energy Research, 2021). Public transport usage in Norway is high, with nearly 20% of passenger-kilometres per day made by public transport. However, cycling rates are lower compared to other Nordic countries. Norway's extensive use of ferries, due to its coastal geography, also distinguishes the Norwegian transport system from many other European countries (Nordregio, 2024).

There are several policies, instruments and initiatives in Innlandet County that support various aspects of rural development. In what follows, we describe some of them.

4.5 Policies and strategies supporting rural and regional development

The “**Regional Plan for the Inclusive Inland**” (Innlandet fylkeskommune, 2023) is a plan that maps the direction for social development and contributes towards shared initiatives towards inclusion in Innlandet. The Innland County's strategic guidelines for the new regional plan a) offering a good education, adapted to secure the opportunity to learn throughout life, b) including a well-developed working life with room for everyone, c) evidencing attractive and vibrant cities and local communities with a varied and rich art and culture life for everyone, and d) where a diverse voluntary sector stimulates participation and high quality of life. The Region plan has three prioritized investment areas: competence and lifelong learning; working life and workplace development; as well as, local communities, meeting places, and culture (Innlandet fylkeskommune, 2023).

The program of action in the Regional Plan for the Inclusive Inland (Innlandet fylkeskommune, 2023) has several areas of investment, and one of them is **Diverse and Equal working life**, where they hope to increase recruitment within industry, health, or other industries with a need for labour. They will work through knowledge-based collaboration and experience-sharing to create an inclusive and equal working life for all. The goal is that people with disabilities, health challenges, and absences from work, education, or training will be engaged in working life. Everyone who can and wants to work should be allowed to do so. Another investment area is **Housing development in rural areas**, and the local convenience store as a meeting place and welfare centre in small communities (as a focal point for

village life). The convenience store is becoming increasingly important as a meeting place and for people's access to groceries and welfare services in small and sparsely populated rural areas. Therefore, a project called the Merkur Program was launched to strengthen knowledge and collaboration about the convenience store in local community development in the Innland (Innlandet fylkeskommune, 2023). The Merkur Program (Merkur-programmet, 2025) is the Ministry of Local Government and Regional Development program for developing and strengthening convenience stores in rural Norway. The Merkur Program is part of The Centre of Competence on Rural Development, that is a “government agency dedicated to strengthening rural municipalities and regions` ability to develop attractive communities” (Distrikssenteret, 2025). The Merkur Program’s goal is to ensure that people in rural districts have access to a convenience store and a bookstore and receive financial support for investments related to the convenience stores (Merkur-programmet, 2025).

The program of action specifies how to achieve the goals in the Region Plan for the Inclusive Innland and for the Kongsvinger Region: they have an **inter-municipal political council** that is a political cooperation by six municipalities in the Kongsvinger region (KIPR), consisting of Eidskog, Grue, Kongsvinger, Nord-Odal, Sør-Odal and Åsnes municipality (The Kongsvinger region, 2024). “KIPR shall contribute to the positive development of the region and look after the citizens' interests across municipal boundaries and levels of administration. KIPR will promote the region's interests in a county and national context” (The Kongsvinger region, 2024).

The Kongsvinger Region has had a three-year long project called “**Youth Inclusion in the Kongsvinger Region**”. “The primary objective of the project has been to address and mitigate social exclusion among young individuals aged 18-35 who are not engaged in either education or the labour market” (Sønderskov, 2024, p.4). The project's results emphasize the importance of more adaptable co-created platforms where stakeholders from local communities can come together to address shared challenges (Sønderskov, 2024). This project has contributed to new knowledge and laid the foundation for municipalities to continue this work in the future (Ung inkludering, 2024).

The project **Young in Innlandet** was launched in November 2024. This is a project a collaboration with the Innlandet, Competence Centre for Substance Abuse (KORUS) and the County Governor that will work together on developing a joint knowledge base about youth (Innlandet fylkeskommune, 2024).

Program for Public Health Work in the Municipalities (Helsedirektoratet, 2018) is a ten-year initiative (2017-2027) to develop the municipalities' work to promote the population's health and quality of life. The development work contributes to strengthening the municipalities' long-term and systematic public health work; and children and young people's mental health and substance abuse prevention are central topics. In Innlandet, 3 years of the current program period remains. The collaborative actors in this program are the Norwegian Directorate of Health, The Norwegian Association of Local and Regional Authorities (KS), municipalities, Innlandet County, Research and development environments, and competence environments.

5. Vulnerability and social exclusion in the Kongsvinger Region

5.1 Social exclusion and poverty

Few people live in extreme poverty in Norway, but relative poverty exists. Relative poverty takes into account the opportunities one has compared to others to live a fulfilling life. **The share of people with relatively low income is higher in Innlandet compared to the national level.** In the Kongsvinger Region the share is higher in all municipalities than the share for Norway and Innlandet, with the exception of Sør-Odal.

Table 14: Share of people with low income, EU scale 60 percent. 2022. Norway, Innlandet and municipalities in the Kongsvinger Region.

	EU scale 60 percent, 2022
Norway	10.9
Innlandet	11.6
Kongsvinger	13.4
Nord-Odal	11.8
Sør-Odal	9.1
Eidskog	13.0
Grue	14.5
Åsnes	14.5

Source:(Statistics Norway, 2024g)

Table 15: Unemployment rate april 2024, Norway, Innlandet and municipalities in the Kongsvinger Region.

	Unemployment rate, april 2024
Norway	2.0
Innlandet	1.8
Kongsvinger	1.8

Nord-Odal	1.9
Sør-Odal	1.7
Eidskog	2.3
Grue	2.3
Åsnes	1.9

Source:(Innlandsstatistikk, 2024b)

Table 16: Share of NEETs 2022, age 15-29. Norway, Innlandet and the municipalities of the Kongsvinger Region. Source:(Innlandsstatistikk, 2024e)

	NEETs age 15-29
Norway	9.5
Innlandet	9.8
Kongsvinger	11.1
Nord-Odal	10.4
Sør-Odal	10.6
Eidskog	12.9
Grue	12.8
Åsnes	10.4

Source:(Innlandsstatistikk, 2024b)

In the white paper “*No one left out – A comprehensive policy to include more people in working life and society*” (Meld. St. 32, (2020-2021)), they emphasize the importance of “*having a job to go to and the value of experiencing social connectedness and fellowship*” (Meld. St. 32, (2020–2021), p. 1). Furthermore, the white paper states that public efforts are insufficient to prevent and counteract social exclusion. It is also underlined that **collaborations with voluntary organisations and social entrepreneurs offers important opportunities to participate and be included in community life**. Moreover, these types of collaborations are something that the government will continue to facilitate (Meld. St. 32, (2020-2021)). Social entrepreneurs are valuable partners in expanding participation in work and social activities by creating and implementing innovative solutions. They provide alternative

pathways into the workforce and play a role in promoting social inclusion and community life (Meld. St. 32, (2020-2021), p.18).

5.2 Disadvantaged groups

According to the interviewees, the Kongsvinger Region faces challenges related to social exclusion. Social exclusion affects a considerable portion of the population, particularly **youth**. Social inclusion typically occurs through education and workplace participation. Conversely, those not engaging in these areas often find themselves socially excluded. The region has a high number of people outside the workforce and the educational system.

This social exclusion extends beyond youth to the broader population, particularly affecting the **elderly**. The region faces an aging population without corresponding population growth, except for newcomers from other municipalities or immigrants. With low fertility rates, the region relies heavily on immigrants and newcomers. Since the region is considered inexpensive to live in, according to the interviewees, many of the newcomers in the region are close to retirement or are retired. Since many of the newcomers are older people, they often require more supporting services, rather than contributing to the workforce, which in turn challenges the region's ability to support the older population and the older newcomers.

According to the interviewees, another challenge in the region is that the **immigrants** often experience social exclusion due to language barriers. Some immigrants form their own networks, further complicating their integration into the broader community.

Given these challenges, according to the interviewees, it is important to address social exclusion comprehensively, as the region cannot afford to marginalise anyone.

According to the interviewees, having a historical and geographical perspective on the challenges they face in the Kongsvinger Region is necessary. The Kongsvinger Region is a border region to Sweden, encompassing vast outback areas. The region also has a **history in forestry and forestry energy**. Historically, the region also had **industrial manufacturing enterprises** and manual occupations that did not require higher education for entry into the job market.

Another factor that the interviewees emphasized was **socially inherited characteristics** and how this was connected with social exclusion over generations. Individuals experiencing social exclusion tend to isolate themselves, forming communities with others in similar situations. This is particularly prevalent among young individuals aged 18-35 who are not engaged in education or the labour market.

Living in the region is inexpensive, and housing is particularly affordable, which attracts many immigrants who may already be marginalized and facing financial challenges. These factors often influence their decision to move to the area. Additionally, the region is characterized by large **geographical distances** and numerous **small-scale communities**, further impacting social dynamics and the challenges of integration.

The interviewees mention that vulnerable groups are young adults who are not engaged in either education or the labour market. In the group of young adults, many of them who are considered socially excluded had a lot of sick leave or challenges at school, school dropout and many were diagnosed with cognitive difficulties. During the interview some mentioned that one contributing factor for the younger group could be that some **parents lacked a driver's licence or a car**, making it impossible for them to drive their children to sports activities such as football training. Although **recreational activities** for children and young people are available, recruiting those who are already socially excluded is challenging. It is easy to reach well-resourced parents, but those already socially excluded remain isolated. Another factor that came up during the interviews was the large geographical distances in the region, which exacerbated the experience of isolation.

People with disabilities are especially vulnerable to social exclusion.

"Our environment is not always organized with a universal design, which can result in a double exclusion for this group" – Interview.

The lack of universal design can contribute significantly to vulnerability. Some informants discussed universal design and that the focus often centres on individuals with physical/visual disabilities. However, some also emphasized that it applies to other disabilities, including reduced cognitive functioning. One of the interviewees said that *"how information is presented on a poster, including the choice of font, can impact accessibility and lead to social exclusion if not designed universally."*

Standing out from the majority in any way can increase a person's vulnerability. This can relate to various factors such as economy, social capital, academic achievements, employment opportunities, self-perception, and self-esteem. Feeling different can have a profound negative impact on an individual. **Social heritage, poor economy, and poor physical and mental health are significant factors contributing to social exclusion and vulnerability.**

"Those who have been socially excluded for generations may become accustomed to their situation and may not try to include themselves socially". –Interview

Social heritage plays a role, with some families experiencing social exclusion for generations.

Once you have been socially excluded, it becomes more difficult to become socially included and to get to know somebody. If you have a disability, it makes it even harder to get to know other people. During the interviews, several mentioned the importance of different meeting places and inclusion activities, but they were mostly sports-based, and this did not suit the needs of everyone.

"Not everyone wants to play sports" - Interview.

The different arenas for social inclusion, such as voluntary organizations, are often for people over 50 years and older, and **younger groups lack meeting arenas**. This makes it harder for young adults to meet others of the same age group.

Social exclusion can lead to significant isolation. This vulnerability has severe consequences not only for individuals but also for society as a whole, making it a substantial societal challenge. For those

experiencing social exclusion, the impact can be extreme. One of the interviewees explained that not getting invited to social events leads to loneliness when one does not have a social network.

There is a duality in the perception of what can be called "**diagnosis society**": some interviews emphasized that diagnosis can lead to some people "becoming their diagnoses", since the diagnosis they have received becomes an inhibitor in everyday life. To the contrary, in one of the interviews a person considered that having disability and receiving a diagnosis, even though there is a strong societal aversion to diagnosing individuals, receiving a diagnosis can be crucial.

"Personally, obtaining a diagnosis has been essential; without it, I would have continued to struggle without the necessary support and rights I now have" – Interview.

The empirical material collected through interviews does not provide a sufficient basis to comment on gender differences related to occurrence and differences in social exclusion. In 2021, Statistics Norway reported that men are overrepresented among those aged 15-29 who have experienced social exclusion. Their analysis was based on the Income and Wealth Statistics for Households, and Statistics on Connection to Work, Education, and Welfare Schemes (Statistics Norway, 2021). However, Norway is one of only a few countries where there is no substantial gender gap in the NEET (Not in Education, Employment, or Training) rate. Young women in Norway are not more likely than young men to be outside of work, education, or training, unlike in most other OECD countries (Fyhn et al., 2021).

6. Assets and potential in the region

During the interviews, several mentioned that the region has many dedicated individuals who are enthusiastic about their profession or role in society. These enthusiasts have driven several voluntary organizations and social innovations have emerged. For example, some organizations have found ways to include the most vulnerable groups in activities where they can excel and feel a sense of belonging.

"Informal relationships can counteract social exclusion and vulnerability. Meeting someone in the support system, such as a coach or a school mentor, who sees and cares about you can make a significant difference." – Interview

There is **potential for collaboration across municipalities**, and more **regional cooperation** could be beneficial. The establishment of the **University Centre** in Kongsvinger and the Science Park has opened up opportunities for young people and adults to pursue higher education and continuing further education. The university offers higher education tailored to the private and public sectors, customized courses, and continuing and further education in various areas of identified need. The importance of these educational opportunities for the region is widely recognized. However, it was recently announced that some of these programs will be discontinued, which is unfortunate given the long-standing efforts to establish them. According to an interviewee, this region needs **predictability and stability in its study programs**, as education is closely linked to social inclusion, employment, and quality of life. Given the region's need for a robust workforce, there is enormous potential to attract and integrate more workers to meet this demand.

An interviewee expressed frustration over the professional coordination to support young people who experience social exclusion. The interviewee emphasized that children and young people mustn't be given the runaround by systems that involve different professional actors from different agencies. Further, the interviewee expressed concerns about how the Norwegian Labour and Welfare Administration works is today for young people who get a work assessment allowance with a three-year limit. This is considered insufficient, especially for socially excluded young people. The interviewee suggested that young people need time to mature, discover their identity, and receive help before they are ready for work training. Work assessment allowance ensures that people between 18 and 67 years of age have an income in periods of illness or injury. To receive a work assessment allowance, the applicant must demonstrate that their ability to work has been impaired by at least 50 percent, and that they need treatment to improve their ability to work or receive help from the Norwegian Labour and Welfare Administration to either retain or find work (Norwegian Labour and Welfare Administration, 2024).

During the interviews, several emphasized that the region needs to ensure a form of **universal design** that effectively supports the most vulnerable. The lack of meeting places with a universal design and a low threshold where one can hang out, play board games, talk, or buy a cup of coffee was pointed out as important.

The focus should not solely be on late intervention but must start early. **Preventive measures, low-threshold initiatives, and interdisciplinary cooperation have potential.**

"We need to foster a culture where everyone goes the extra mile, such as making an additional phone call or offering to carpool for football training and other activities" – Interview focus group.

Some of the interviewees considered early intervention important and were frustrated when people don't take things seriously or failed to show adequate concern.

"I've often heard remarks like: we already knew when he/she was a child that it was going to be like this" - Interview focus group.

Initiatives aimed at social inclusion, particularly regarding entry into the workforce, should be meaningful for those it may concern. Initiatives should align with the individual's aspirations for further work or education and be driven by their motivations.

According to the interviews, early intervention starts from the moment women are pregnant and visit the health centre. If there are clear signs indicate that a person is at risk of social exclusion, measures are immediately put in place.

While the municipality offers various free activities for children and young people, accessing these resources often requires applying for approval. This process can be stigmatizing, as the threshold to admit financial need can be high. Families accustomed to generational social exclusion may not even attempt to integrate socially.

One tool in diminishing vulnerability is the subsidy from the municipality to take on "**summer job activities**" looking after children of primary school age. The summer job activity hires young people as activity coordinators. The young people then have the opportunity to gain work experience. The young people have to apply and attend an interview, where they can earn their own money for the first time in their lives and experience a sense of achievement. Around 150 young people get summer jobs through this, and it is a mix of young people who could easily secure a job elsewhere, and those who are socially excluded or vulnerable.

"It has been important that not only "problematic youth" or those who are socially excluded should get this job, so that getting the job should not become a stigma in itself." - Interview focus group.

Several strategies and initiatives exist to reduce inequalities in the county and the region; some are more explicit, and some are more implicit. The "Regional Plan for the Inclusive Innlandet" (Innlandet fylkeskommune, 2023) sets the direction for social development and contributes to a common effort for inclusion in Innlandet, as previously explained in the report.

There are many different **voluntary organizations** in the Kongsvinger Region that are socially inclusive and driven by motivated enthusiasts. These organizations range from sports activities to organizations such as the Red Cross that contribute towards the strengthening of the local community.

7. Conclusion and potential focus of MAP

The Kongsvinger Region has had a slight decrease in population over the last decades and has a higher share of the older population than of the child population. Innlandet County is the only county in Norway with a “birth deficit” with fewer births each year than necessary to maintain the population size over time. The Kongsvinger Region also has a lower employment rate and lower share of people who have completed a university education than average for Innlandet and Norway.

The main challenge in the region is social exclusion, which involves social exclusion from education and the labour market. Interviewees emphasised that the labour market and education are important arenas for social inclusion.

It is crucial to establish social areas that are designated for youth, the elderly, and individuals with immigrant backgrounds. The social arenas must have a universal design and a low threshold. As the interviews demonstrate, vulnerable groups such as youth often find themselves lost in a web of bureaucratic routes. Social arenas could benefit them by being more socially inclusive through activities, as meeting places, or the equivalent, which would empower them.

Given that youth and the elderly are particularly prone to social exclusion in the Kongsvinger Region, social entrepreneurs whose work is directed towards these age groups should be supported at the regional as well as national level. A systematic mapping of the needs of these particular groups would provide valuable insights into ongoing efforts to combat social exclusion.

Some bullet points that might be potential focal points for the MAP:

- Ensure universal design and social inclusion in mind at every stage,
- Social arenas for different age groups with low thresholds. As mentioned throughout this report, social entrepreneurs play an essential role in enhancing social inclusion by providing alternative pathways to work and community life,
- Social arenas across different age groups and cultures.

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8.1 List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Full name
MAP	Multi-Acor Platform
UN	United Nations
NAV	The Norwegian Labour and Welfare Administration
NIPH	The Norwegian Institute of Public Health
NHO	Confederation of Norwegian Enterprise
EU	European Union
KS	The Norwegian Association of Local and Regional Authorities
KORUS	Competence Centre for the field of Substance Abuse
KIPR	Inter-municipal political council that is a political cooperation for six municipalities in the Kongsvinger Region
NEET	Not in Education, Employment or Training
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development

9. Partners

